

UNCONTROLLED COMMUNICATIONS AND CONSUMER RESPONSES IN THE TELECOMMUNICATIONS INDUSTRY IN THE SOUTH-SOUTH GEOPOLITICAL ZONE OF NIGERIA

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Abstract: *Unsolicited information spreads like wild fire, particularly because of the internet. Thus, what organizations cannot control is capable of affecting positively or negatively, both the organization and the consumers. The aim of this work was to examine the effect of uncontrolled communications on consumer responses in the telecommunications industry in the South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. Uncontrolled communications had word of mouth (WOM) communications and publicity as its independent proxies while consumer responses were measured by consumer preference, brand attitude and brand re-use intention as the dependent variables. The researchers adopted the survey research design on a usable sample size of 355 respondents drawn from three senatorial districts of Akwa Ibom, Rivers and Delta states. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse the data obtained through a structured questionnaire titled “Uncontrolled Communications and Consumer Response Questionnaire” (UCCRQ). The test of hypotheses was done with the use of multiple regressions and ANOVA. The results of the analyses showed positive and significant effects of the uncontrolled communications on the three separate consumer responses. Thus, the researchers concluded that uncontrolled communications has a significant and positive effect on consumer preference, brand attitude and brand re-use intention. They recommended among other things, that there is a need for the Management of the studied telecommunications companies, namely MTN, Globacom, Airtel Nigeria and 9Mobile, to continue to build their service quality and delivery systems around integrity, credibility and humanity in order to enhance their companies’ reputation and customers’ trust which will make customers talk positively and persuasively about the firms.*

Keywords: *Uncontrolled communications, WOM communications, publicity, consumer responses, consumer preference, brand attitude, brand re-use intention*

Introduction

Nigeria is at an age of information mongering. Unfortunately today, the advent of ICT which has a lot of deliverables to individuals, companies, sectors, communities and the global world, equally carry tons of defamatory and malicious misinformation about everything. Many companies have been

affected by this negative trend, which have had their products being given bad publicity globally. For instance, a lot of people in Nigeria have stopped drinking Nigeria coca cola (coke) because content creators, skit writers and publicity/fame-crazy individuals demonstrate online with this product as an agent in cleaning different surfaces and substances at home, making the viewing world to interpret it as containing harmful substances detrimental to human health.

Uncontrolled communications is any communication carried out or messages disseminated about a company and its offering which is not under the control of the company. Uncontrolled communications runs like wild fire, making it necessary that firms guide their actions and guard their products from being at the receiving end of malicious information in the social media that easily sway people. According to Mfon (2021), uncontrolled communications refer to (WOM) communications and publicity communication sources that influence GSM companies' subscribers' to respond to these GSM companies. In the context of this study, uncontrolled communications refer to WOM communication and publicity.

WOM communication is a strong force that can work in favour of or disfavour of the object of focus. It is any kind of communication that freely passes between people about a product or a company. It could be in the form of conversations, discussions, recommendations, reviews, suggestions, etc, drawn from people's experiences and shared with others that could aid them in making a decision concerning a purchase. It is very natural for people to discuss certain products or brands that are particularly popular. And consumers rely so much on such information since most times they are deemed to be accurate and reliable.

Publicity is another independent source of information that consumers regard as authentic and reliable. This independence is in the sense that this information is not under the direct control of the respective companies mentioned in the information. Publicity is information that comes in the form of publicity announcement, public service announcement, news information, etc. Ayeni (2007), reiterates that publicity is any message about an organization or its product(s) that is communicated through the mass media, but is not paid for by the organization. This form of information is deemed to be reliable just like WOM and more dominant than marketer-driven communication.

Basically, these two forms of information (WOM and publicity) elicit responses from consumers who seek to gather information outside the purview of the organization about the organization's offerings. The responses from consumers could be in the form of preference for a product, forming an attitude towards the brand or decisions to re-use the brand. Whichever reactions are triggered from the consumers, companies wish them to be positive and favourable towards the products on offer. Thus, these responses are very important where the consumer is concerned. Preference means that the consumer will make a particular choice among alternative offers. Brand attitude spells the overall evaluation of a brand whether good or bad while re-use intention indicates the willingness of the consumer to buy the particular brand of choice over and over again.

Thus, these responses which have a reflection on company's sales vis a vis their revenue and profit levels, provide service providers concrete evidence for measuring the effectiveness of brand communications so as to attain the goals of communication and ultimately the corporate goals of the organization (Mfon, 2021). It was therefore, the intent of the researchers to examine uncontrolled communications in relation to consumer responses in the telecommunications industry in the South-South Zone of Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The advent of the internet has opened up both positive and negative influences on the daily life and relationships of people. Information is readily available to users on any kind of products or issue. Most consumers would resort to personal sources of information rather than trust the information that emanates from the companies. Thus, WOM communication has been under the lime light to highlight its advantages and disadvantages for a long time.

For instance, Tang and To (2015), investigated the relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction, and informal communication in the telecom business. Grace and O'Cass' (2005), in their research, studied three communication avenues which are the controlled communications, uncontrolled communications, and brand names in order to determine their influence on consumer service brand evaluation. Ahmed and Rouf (2015), carried out a similar study in Bangladesh. Mfon (2021), did same in the South-South Zone of Nigeria, but with a focus on consumer responses. Mfon and Uford (2024), restricted their study to the effect of controlled communications on consumer responses in the South-South Nigeria. Samadi, *et al*, (2009), studied brand dimensions and re-purchase intention. Cheung, *et al* (2012), examined the electronic WOM (eWOM) communication with a literature analysis and integrative model. Mfon and Uford (2022), investigated the preferences of consumers as they relate with choices in fast food restaurants in Uyo. Gabeur (2015), considered the consumer's behaviour facing WOM and its impact from marketing point of view.

Several other works have been done on WOM communications, publicity and different dimensions of consumer responses. But there is gap in literature as to the effect of uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) on three dimensions of consumer responses namely; consumer preference, consumer brand attitude and brand re-use intention in the South-South Zone of Nigeria. It was therefore, the intent of the researchers to study the effect of uncontrolled communications with special emphasis on consumer preference, brand attitude and brand re-use intentions in order to provide literature to fill the identified gap.

Research Objectives

The broad objective of this study was to determine the effect of uncontrolled communications on consumer responses in the telecommunications industry in the South-South Geopolitical Zone, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to;

- ❖ Determine the effect of uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) on the consumer preference for GSM brands in the telecommunications industry in the South-South Zone, Nigeria.
- ❖ Ascertain the effect of uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) on brand attitude in the telecommunications industry in the South-South Zone, Nigeria
- ❖ Establish the effect of uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) on GSM brand re-use intention in the telecommunications industry in the South-South Zone, Nigeria.

Research Questions

- What is the effect of uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) on the consumer preference for GSM brands in the telecommunications industry in the South-South Zone of Nigeria?
- How do uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) affect GSM consumer brand attitude in the telecommunications industry in the South-South Zone of Nigeria?
- What is the effect of uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) on the GSM brand re-use intention in the telecommunications industry in the South-South Zone of Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

- Ho₁** There is no significant effect of uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) on the consumer preference for GSM brands.
- Ho₂** Uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) do not significantly affect consumer attitude towards GSM brands.
- Ho₃** Uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) do not significantly determine brand re-use intention.

Review of Related Literature

Uncontrolled communications

Besides the communication style that a company adopts and pays for, information about the organization and its products is usually circulated through uncontrolled means. This means that messages about the product/organization spread through means that the organization does not pay for and is not directly responsible for. Mangold, Miller and Brockway (1999), assert that such messages are not market-driven and consumers deem them to be more credible. These channels include WOM communication and publicity. These channels exert significant influences on the way the customers respond to organizations.

WOM Communication

WOM, which was first coined by Whyte in the literature in 1954, is a form of communication between/among marketers and consumers (Demirbas, 2017). Mahapatra and Saputra (2021), defined WOM as a “communication process in the form of providing recommendations both individually and in groups for a product or service that aims to provide personal information”. According to Rai and Tripathi (2021), WOM “is an oral, written and electronic communication between people related to the advantages or experiences of buying or using a product or service”. Ennew (2000), adds that

WOM communication could be positive or negative. The bottom line is that WOM communication occurs between/among consumers who share their experiences about a product that they have bought or consumed. Thus, WOM is just a conversation about a product/products and usually occurs face to face. It comprises any suggestion, recommendation, comments and conversation people make about a product. Mfon (2021), operationalised WOM as referring “to referrals and good talk about GSM companies from sources other than the organization, that influence subscribers’ response to GSM companies”.

Publicity

Uncontrolled communications is equally captured by publicity. Mfon (2021) operationalised publicity as publicity announcement, news information and public service announcement about MTN, Globacom, Airtel and 9Mobile as perceived by subscribers. Ayeni, (2007), sees publicity to be any message about an organization or its product(s) that is communicated through the mass media, but is not paid for by the organization. This form of message communication is similar to WOM in the sense that publicity is also viewed as a reliable source of information that is more dominant than marketer-driven communications (Ahluwalia *et al*, 2000). Another similarity is that negative publicity is said to have a greater influence on consumer response than positive (Grace & O’Cass, 2005). However, Marconi (2004) claims that publicity is “largely connected to positive awareness”. In addition, Hauss (1993) supports this position that, regarding the attitudes of people towards political parties, there is no doubt that good and bad media coverage has a profound effect. While unfavourable publicity can lead to negative perceptions, positive publicity can improve attitudes (Hauss, 1993).

Consumer Responses

The intent of companies sending out messages/information about their brands to their target markets is to elicit some kind of responses, mostly favourable ones from them. They try to be as persuasive enough in their messages so that the target markets will respond. The response could be in the form of patronage or intention to buy. For this to happen, the company must understand their target markets, taking into consideration their intents, desires and wants and crafting messages that can touch the hearts and minds of this group. Having an insight into the customers’ ways of thinking, what motivates them, and their environmental concerns will arm companies with the necessary tactics to woo these customers to respond favourable to the company’s messages.

Consumer response is exhibited in the behaviour of the consumer. Consumer behaviour refers to the act of consuming goods and services (Ramesh & Prasad, 2012). It incites consumers to choose between several competing services. According to Calin (2014), consumers make buying decisions according to their emotional desires. Many other aspects of consumer behaviour are considered in addition to what to buy, where, how often and frequent use of service. They include; consumer preference, purchase intentions, brand image, brand attitudes, etc. This study adopts the definition of

consumer responses as given by Mfon (2021), which refers to “customer preference, brand attitude and brand re-use intention as regards MTN, Globacom, Airtel and 9Mobile services”.

Consumer preference

The intangibility of service products alter the way consumers respond to information on service offerings and the way they shop for them. The way customers choose and evaluate services offerings should be the concern of service providers (Grace and O’Cass, 2005), as services are sought for, and evaluated in dissimilar pattern than physical products. This dissimilarity is attributed to the interesting characteristics of services plus the high experience quality inherent in services. In this manner, customers think that it is progressively hard to survey services when contrasted with physical products. Several studies (e.g., Kotler, 2012; Zeithaml, 2003; Attih, Ikpe & Mfon, 2017) propose that the principal characteristics that make a service administration not the same as physical merchandise are: “intangibility, variability, inseparability, perishability and lack of ownership”.

Consumer preference is a term that refers to consumer’s choices to maximize their satisfaction. According to Mfon and Uford (2024), customer preference is the subscribers’ attachment to selected GSM brands based on service suppliers’ targeted communication source, unsolicited information and brand name. The preference of customers, as indicated by Novemsky, Dhar, Schwarz and Simonson (2007), is seen as a positive inspiration and enthusiasm demonstrated towards a product. Consumer preference is used basically to mean an alternative that has the best foreseen incentives among various choices. Preferences can be activated by the features related with the physical outlook of the product/service (shape, size, print, taste, shading, consistency, bundle, etc); components concerned with the label name, user instructions that go with the item; the statue granted to the individual owning and using that specific item.

According to Mfon and Uford (2024), consumers have a hierarchy of attributes they consider very important to them in building preferences for a particular product. What may be important for the selection of one product may differ when another product is involved. The bottom line remains the presence of attributes that cut across the needs of consumers. In telecommunication industries, Opele, Afolabi and Onifade (2018) contended that, the service organizations need to consider good customer service, competitive pricing, attractive promotion, as well as stable network service.

In the wake of deciding to build consumer preference towards a brand, the producer can consider the following measures: change the item; change the convictions concerning the contending brands; change the significance of features; attract attention towards ignored highlights; change the consumers’ ideals.

Brand attitude

Brand attitude spells the overall evaluation of a brand, whether good or bad (Low & Lamb, 2000). Brand attitude refers to the meaning that is captured in the mind of the consumer when a brand is mentioned which determines whether the buyer will buy or not. Brand attitude is also described as

the basis of the activities of customers, a favourable or unfavourable evaluation, emotional sensation, and behaviour propensity that an individual holds. It is the overall impression that a consumer holds about a brand. This implies that positive brand attitudes are important for the long term success and growth of a brand.

In the view point of Yi and Suh (2005), three factors stand out as being the determinants of brand attitude. These factors include the experience of the customers with the service, the image of the brand and communication tools that are adopted in communicating the brand. These factors in turn influence brand loyalty. Whatever feelings the customer forms for the service brand will trigger the intention to purchase and reuse the service. Consequently, when the user or customer is satisfied with a service, there is the chance for the customer to create an attachment to the service. Thus, Raajpoot and Ghilni-Wage (2019) identified cognitive and affect processes of evaluation as triggers of brand attitude. In Mfon (2021), brand attitude is operationalised as the overall evaluation of the respective brands by subscribers of MTN, Glo, Airtel and 9Mobile.

Brand Re-use Intention

As the name implies, brand re-use intention is the customer's readiness and willingness to use a brand again and again. The intention-to-use is defined as a "precise need to continue a relationship with a service provider" (Boshooof & Gray, 2004). Bhattacharjee (2001), argued that the successful performance of the service system should not be based on simple, instantaneous use, but on sustainable reuse intention. Choi and Sun (2016) defined re-use intention as "the level of consumers' subjective preferences for using the services again and for recommending this service to family and friends". Before customers use these services, they have specific requirements in mind. On the basis of these needs and after browsing the related information given initial experiences, customers filter, evaluate and compare the information/services and subsequently make a rational decision to select the same service again.

Individuals decide themselves and independently when and with which branded telecommunication network they want to use (Yang, Kim & Yoo 2013). Hence, marketers have already bridged the gap of capturing the consumer's interest as soon as they connect to the network. However, the telecommunications companies still do not know how consumers feel about using their brands. Thus, it is ideal to examine and understand the consumer attitude towards telecommunications network and reuse intention within the consumers' immediate response. In the context of telecommunications network, reuse intention seems to be important to predict behavioural outcomes (i.e, reuse) assuming that frequent use strengthens the brand relationship by enhancing brand attitudes (Berger & Mitchell, 1989). Generally, reuse intention refers to the intention raised by consumers to maintain regular contact with the same network (e.g., Cronin, Brady & Hult 2000). Mfon (2021), operationalized re-use intention as the subscribers' willingness to use the services of the MTN, Globacom, Airtel and 9Mobile companies, again and again.

Review of Empirical Literature

Grace and O’Cass (2005) studied service brand communications (controlled communications, uncontrolled communications, brand names) and consumer brand evaluation. Among other things, the result showed that WOM had a significant influence only on brand re-use intentions. They therefore recommended that information derived from all communication avenues should be employed to decide future purchase decisions of the consumers.

Tand and To (2015), investigated the link between service quality, customer satisfaction and WOM communications of telecommunications services, using a sample size of 275 consumers in Macao. A path-way analysis which was used to analyse the data showed that service quality was connected with WOM

Samadi, Bahman and Dehghan (2009) investigated the effect of brand dimensions on customer repurchase intention of Refah Chain stores in Tehran City. The results indicated that brand evidence and brand communication have a positive impact on satisfaction, attitudes, behavioural intentions and customer loyalty.

Javadeyn, Amini and Amini, (2010), examined the effect of brand equity on industrial customer loyalty. The findings showed that brand equity and trust are the factors that most importantly influence behavioural and attitudinal patterns of customers’ loyalty.

Methodology of Research

Research Design

The methodology of this research was the survey research design adopted for its ability to investigate the opinions of respondents at the time of the occurrence of the phenomena under study.

Population/Sampling/Sampling Procedure

Subscribers of MTN, Globacom, Airtel and 9Mobile who were active voice customers, resident in the South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria, at the time of this research, served as the population of the study. According to information from the National Communication Commission, as at June 2019, their number stood at 24,751,262 (from www.ncc.gov.ng and www.businessday.ng).

The Taro Yamane formula for sample size determination was applied to the population to obtain the sample size of 400. According to Taro Yamane, the formula for determining sample size is given as

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where: N = population

n = sample size

e = error limit (0.05) on the basis of 95% confidence level

$$\text{Therefore } n = \frac{24751262}{1+24751262(0.05)^2} = \frac{24751262}{1+24751262(0.0025)} = \frac{24751262}{1+61878.155} = \frac{24751262}{61879.155} = 399.994 = 400$$

$$n \approx 400$$

The first step the researchers took in the sampling procedure was to place the six states in the South-South Geopolitical Zone based on their geographical contiguity and cultural affiliation. Akwa Ibom State was placed against Cross River; Rivers against Bayelsa and Edo against Delta. A simple random

sampling by shuffling and picking was done which resulted in Akwa Ibom, Rivers and Delta states being picked from the six states.

From the selected states, the three senatorial districts were stratified and two churches each were conveniently picked from each senatorial district. The reason for using churches was that the churches provided central locations for contacting all the different classes of people who are subscribers of the studied services. Lastly, respondents who were to participate in the study were selected using a proportionate random sampling method according to the number of subscribers in each state. Thus, a sample size of 400 respondents was drawn as follows;

Rivers State	=	159
Delta State	=	128
Akwa Ibom State	=	113

Table 3.1 shows the different states of the South-South Geopolitical Zone, the number of LGAs, the population distribution and the sampled states and samples drawn.

Table 3.1:Capital cities, number of local government areas, population distribution and sampled states and samples

S/n	State	Capital City	No. of LGA	Population Distribution	Sampled size of Respondent
1	Akwa Ibom	Uyo	31	3902051	113
2	Cross River	Calabar	18	2892988	-
3	Rivers	Port Harcourt	22	5198716	159
4	Bayelsa	Yenegoa	9	1704515	-
5	Delta	Asaba	25	4112445	128
6	Edo	Benin	18	3233366	-

Source: (NBS, 2011; nigeria.opendataforafrica.org; Ikoba *et al*, 2018/ Researchers’ Field Survey)

In selecting the subjects for the study, pieces of papers inscribed with “yes” and “no” were folded into a bag. Respondents in each church in each of the senatorial districts that made up the study sample were asked to pick a paper from the bag. All those who picked “yes” were considered subjects for the study. A total of 400 respondents spread across the three senatorial districts of the three selected states constituted the sample for the study. Trusted and reliable agents, alongside leaders in the churches, helped to administer the copies of questionnaire.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The researchers decided to name the questionnaire used as instrument for the collection of data, “Uncontrolled Communications and Consumer Response Questionnaire” (UCCRQ). The instrument, before being put into use, was validated by a Professor of Marketing and two other lecturers from the

Department of Measurement and Evaluation, Faculty of Education, University of Uyo. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained by the application of Cronbach Alpha Analysis to two sets of data obtained from 50 students in the Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa, in a test-retest procedure. The analysis yielded a coefficient of .773 which was adjudged to be adequate. Thus, the instrument was proven to be reliable and fit for use for the study.

Instrumentation

The questionnaire dealt with the constructs of the study which were uncontrolled communications (WOM and Publicity) and consumer responses (namely, consumer preference, consumer brand attitude and re-use intention). It was structured on an adjusted four-points Likert Scale ranging from strongly agree, (SA); agree, (A); disagree (D); and strongly disagree, (SD) with the scores of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively.

Section one of the instrument dealt with the independent sub- variables (WOM and publicity) while section two dealt with the three dependent sub-variables (consumer preference, consumer brand attitude and re-use intention). Both sections contained statements which were made to measure each of the sub-variables. The scores were added together to obtain the mean value for each of the statements and the corresponding standard deviations calculated. Thus, for the adjusted four-point scale the mean was $(4+3+2+1=10/4=2.5)$. A mean value of 2.5 and above was considered significant and the statement adjudged to exude the appropriate effect.

Method of Data Analysis

For the analysis of the data, descriptive and inferential statistics were applied. Data in sections A and B of the questionnaire were analysed descriptively with the mean and standard deviations calculated and thereafter used for hypothesis by hypothesis analysis at 0.05 level of significance using Multiple Regression Analysis to show firstly, the average change in the dependent variables as a result of a unit change in the independent variables. Secondly, the degree of the dependent variables that could be explained by the influence of the independent variables, and thirdly, the proportion of the variation in the dependent variables which was caused by extraneous variables. The statistical package for social science (SPSS), a computer based software programme aided in the generation of results. The criterion for the acceptance/rejection of the null hypothesis was;

Accept the null hypothesis if the computed f-ratio is less than the tabulated f-value at 0.05 level of significance and reject the null hypothesis in favour of the alternate if the computed- ratio is higher than the tabulated f-value at 0.05 level of significance.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

From Table 4.1, the copies of questionnaire administered were 400. Out of this number, Rivers state had 159 copies but returned 148 (41.7%) in usable form. Delta state had 128 but returned 105 (29.6%)

in usable form. Akwa Ibom State had 113 but returned 102 (28.7%) in usable form. In the overall, a total of 355 (88.75%) copies of questionnaire were returned in usable form.

Questionnaire Administration and Response Rate

Table 4.1: Questionnaire administration and response rate per the sampled states in the South-South Zone

States sampled	No. of administered questionnaire	No. of Returned questionnaire	Percentage of response
Rivers	159	148	41.7
Delta	128	105	29.6
AkwaIbom	113	102	28.7
Total	400	355	100

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Descriptive Analysis of Responses from Respondents

Table 4.2 presented respondents’ responses on the uncontrolled communication variables

Table 4.2: Uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) in the telecommunications industry in the South-South Zone, Nigeria

Uncontrolled Communication	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Std.
1. I suggest GSM provider(s) for someone to use	191 53.8%	117 32.9%	30 8.5%	17 4.8%	3.321	0.993
2. I hear people discuss a lot about adverts of GSM providers	116 32.7%	135 38.0%	83 23.4%	21 5.9%	2.927	1.164
3. Someone has recommended GSM provider(s) for me	215 60.6%	97 27.3%	33 9.3%	10 2.8%	3.366	1.042
4. I hear people comments on the GSM quality of good network	81 22.8%	61 17.2%	128 36.1%	85 23.9%	1.991	1.095
5. I hear comments on GSM charges rate	236 66.5%	95 26.7%	24 6.8%	- -	3.428	0.891
6. I talk favourably about GSM services	112 31.5%	106 29.9%	99 27.9%	38 10.7%	2.687	1.184
7. I hear people talk favourably about GSM services	107 30.2%	157 44.2%	58 16.3%	33 9.3%	2.275	1.247
8. There is much complaints about GSM operators in my locality	162 45.6%	140 39.5%	42 11.8%	11 3.1%	3.138	1.095
Clustered mean					2.89	1.062

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Table 4.2 presented the uncontrolled communications variables in the telecommunications companies in South-South, Nigeria. The results showed a clustered mean of 2.89 and a standard deviation of 1.062. The implication of these measures is that most respondents were of the opinion

that the variables of uncontrolled communications namely, WOM and publicity, were highly rated. It can therefore be surmised that the subscribers of telecommunications companies responded to the different companies based on uncontrolled communications.

Individual analysis of each statement showed that 236 (66.5%) respondents claimed that they heard comments on GSM charges rate; 215 (60.6%) claimed that someone had recommended GSM provider(s) for them; 191 (53.8%) claimed that they suggest provider(s)for others to use; 162 (45.6%) respondents strongly agreed that they heard much complaints about GSM operators in their locality; 112 (31.5%) and 107 (30.2%) claimed that they talked favourably about GSM services and also heard people talk favourably about GSM services.

Invariably, 128 (36.1%) respondents disagreed with the statement that they heard people’s comments on the GSM quality of network; 99 (27.9%) respondents disagreed that they talked favourably about GSM services. From the results, uncontrolled communications have been the most adopted means of information among GSM subscribers in the study area. This is because, little deliberation and consideration from controlled communications come into play when customers are choosing a cellular network provider mainly for SMS and calls. This is also applied when customers’ interest is basically in internet data plans.

Table 4.3 presented respondents’ responses on the consumer preference variable of consumer responses

Table 4.3: Consumer preference for the telecommunication firms in the South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria

Statement	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Std.
Consumer preference						
1. My brand preference was due to suggestions from family and friends.	173 48.7%	130 36.6%	36 10.1%	16 4.5%	2.923	1.167
2. I preferred my brand due to favourable comments from people on their economical billing method	163 45.9%	74 20.9%	77 21.7%	41 11.5%	2.721	1.271
3. I chose my brand based on other users’ comments around me	219 61.7%	120 33.8%	16 4.5%	- -	3.212	1.087
4. I preferred my brand because, I like the logo, colour and slogan	76 21.4%	69 19.4%	88 24.8%	122 34.4%	2.155	1.174
Clustered mean					2.75	1.175

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Consumer preference for telecommunication companies’ communication in South-South, Nigeria was examined in Table 4.3. From the results, given the clustered mean of 2.75, and standard deviation of 1.175, most respondents expressed their preference based on the different avenues of communication outside the control of the different telecommunications companies. The implication is that

subscribers of telecommunications companies responded to the different companies based on the different aspects of messages/communications emanating directly from the public outside the control of the organizations.

Thus, from the table, 219 (61.7%) respondents strongly agreed that they chose a particular brand of telecommunication firm based on other users' comments about services offered by the firm. This was followed by 173 (48.7%) respondents who strongly agreed that their preferences resulted from suggestions from family members and friends. Equally, 163 (45.9%) respondents agreed that they preferred their brands due to the favourable comments from people on the economical billing method of these companies. However, 122 (34.4%) respondents disagreed that logo, colour and slogan were the basic features that ignited preference for communications from the different telecommunication companies.

Brand Attitude among customers of the studied telecommunication firms in the South-South Zone, Nigeria is examined in Table 4.4

Table 4.4: Brand Attitude among customers of the studied telecommunication firms

Brand Attitude	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Std.
1. A particular comment from a user affected my notion towards a brand	169 47.6%	95 26.8%	65 18.3%	26 7.3%	2.928	1.338
2. I like my brand because I heard that providers are generous and give bonuses	150 42.3%	135 38.0%	51 14.4%	19 5.3%	3.237	1.302
3. I feel very positive about my brands	136 38.3%	113 31.8%	66 18.6%	40 11.3%	2.583	1.336
4. Hearing people chant my preferred brand(s) jingles attracted me.	57 16.1%	63 17.7%	144 40.6%	91 25.6%	2.132	1.272
5. I like my brand because of what others say about their promo packages	196 55.2%	111 31.3%	29 8.2%	19 5.3%	3.397	1.018
Clustered mean					2.75	1.253

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Brand attitude of subscribers towards uncontrolled communications of telecommunications companies in South-South, Nigeria was examined in Table 4.4. From the results, given the clustered mean of 2.75, and standard deviation of 1.253, most respondents expressed positive brand attitude towards the telecommunication companies based on WOM and publicity. The implication is that subscribers of telecommunications companies have formed positive brand attitude based on the different messages/communication emanating from the public.

Thus, from Table 4.4, 196 (55.2%) respondents strongly agreed that they liked their brands because of what people said about the companies' promo packages; 111 (31.3%) agreed; 29 (8.2%) disagreed while 19 (5.3%) strongly disagreed. Other responses and the agreement/disagreement ratings are captured on the table.

Brand re-use intention among customers of the studied telecommunication firms in the South-South Zone, Nigeria are examined in Table 4.5

Table 4.5: Brand re-use intention among customers of the studied telecommunications firms

Brand re-use intention	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Std.
1. If my SIM gets bad/missing, I will still use/go for my brand	210 59.2%	116 32.7%	20 5.6%	9 2.5%	3.454	1.339
2. If I have a chance to give GSM brand to a friend/relative I will buy my brand	142 40.0%	127 35.8%	59 16.6%	27 7.6%	3.003	1.213
3. I will always choose my brand for their promo packages	111 31.3%	88 24.8%	95 26.8%	61 17.2%	2.701	0.983
4. I am willing to stick to my brand, even when new ones try to convince me	169 47.6%	100 28.2%	63 17.7%	23 6.5%	3.101	1.039
5. My brand is so known that I will prefer to remain with it	75 21.1%	53 14.9%	122 34.4%	105 29.6%	1.991	1.023
6. I am willing to pay a price premium over competing brands to be able to purchase this brand again	76 21.4%	44 12.4%	145 40.7%	90 25.4%	1.787	0.912
Clustered mean					2.67	1.083

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Brand re-use intentions among customers of the studied telecommunication firms in the South-South Zone, Nigeria are examined on Table 4.5. From the results, given the clustered mean of 2.67, and standard deviation of 1.083, most respondents expressed their willingness to use their brands in future. The implication is that most subscribers of telecommunication companies, given similar opportunities in future will still go for their used brands. Thus, from the Table, 210 (59.2%) respondents strongly agreed that, if their SIM cards got faulty or missing, they would still use/go for the brand.

This conforms to apriori expectations; because a large percentage of the customers are ever willing to retrieve their contact SIM cards, if damaged or lost. This is because loss of SIM cards invariably means forfeiture of connections. Equally, 169 (47.6%) and 142 (40.0%) respondents strongly agreed that they were willing to stick to their brands, even when new ones try to convince them and that if they had a chance to give GSM brand to a friend/relative they will buy their preferred brand

respectively. Against this, background, 145 (40.7%) respondents disagreed that they were willing to pay a price premium over competing brands to be able to purchase their brands again.

Analysis and Test of Hypotheses

The three hypotheses raised, were tested with multiple regression analysis and analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the strength of the relationship. The test of hypotheses was conducted with the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS), Version 20.

Test of hypothesis 1

There is no significant effect of uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) on the consumer preference for GSM brands. In order to test the hypothesis, two variables were identified as follows:

- (i) Uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity), as the independent variable.
- (ii) Consumer preference as dependent variable.

Uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) were the determining factor influencing consumer preference. This was expressed in equation form as:

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2) \dots\dots\dots 1.$$

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e_i \dots 2$$

Where;

Y = Consumer preference

X₁ = WOM

X₂ = Publicity

β₀ = Intercept

β₁ – β₂ = Parameters estimate

e_i = error term (0.05%)

Therefore, $Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2$

Using the model above, the dependent and independent variables were subjected to regression analysis in order to generate the predicted joint influence of the independent variables X₁(WOM) and X₂ (Publicity) on the dependent variable Y (consumer preference).

Table 4.6: Model summary of multiple regression analysis of uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) on consumer preference.

Variable	Parameters	Coefficient	Std error	Tcal – value
Constant	β ₀	737.994	178.193	4.254 ^{***}
WOM(X ₁)	β ₁	0.737	0.019	38.177 ^{***}
Publicity (X ₂)	β ₂	224.259	44.003	5.096 ^{***}
R-Square (R²)		0.807		
Adjusted R – Square (R⁻²)		0.806		
F – Statistics		734.193		
F – Probability		0.000		
Durbin-Watson stat		2.170		

***, **, and * denotes significance of coefficient at 1%, 5%, and 10% level respectively

Source: SPSS Version 20 Computation

The estimated value of WOM (X_1) was statistically significant and positively related to consumer preference at 1% level. This signifies that WOM has a significant effect on consumer preference for particular telecommunication brands in the study area. Thus, a unit increase in WOM leads to 0.737 unit increase on consumer preference for telecommunication brands in the study area. The result shows that telecommunications companies must consistently offer satisfactory services to maintain their customers and also spur them into speaking well of the company to potential subscribers to woe them to prefer the brand

The result of coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) was 0.807 which implies that, 80.7% variation in the dependent variable was explained by changes in the independent variables, while 19.3% was unexplained by the stochastic variables in the model. The Durbin-Watson stat value was 2.170 which is close to 2.5, implying that there is no evidence of autocorrelation. F-stat value of 734.193 and F-prob value of 0.000 were observed from the analysis which are less than 0.05 (95% degree of freedom), indicating that, the estimated regression model adopted in this study was statistically significant at 5% significant level. With this, the researcher rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternate hypothesis which states that, there is a significant effect of uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) on consumer preference for GSM brands.

Test of hypothesis 2

Uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) do not significantly affect consumer attitude towards GSM brands.

In order to test the hypothesis, two variables were identified as follows:

- (i) Uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity), as the independent variables.
- (ii) Brand attitude as the dependent variable.

Model specification: Brand attitude is estimated to be influenced by uncontrolled communications which are a composite of WOM and publicity. This can be expressed in equation form as:

$Y = f(X_1, X_2) \dots\dots\dots 1$

$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e_i \dots 2$

Where;

Y = Brand attitude

X_1 = WOM

X_2 = Publicity

β_0 = Intercept

$\beta_1 - \beta_2$ = Parameters estimate

e_i = error term (0.05%)

$Y = f(WOM, P.)$, that is, $Y = f(X_1, X_2)$

Therefore, $Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2$

Using the model above, the independent and dependent variables were subjected to regression analysis in order to generate the effect of the independent variables, uncontrolled communications (X_1 , WOM and X_2 , publicity) on the dependent variable Y (brand attitude).

Table 4.7: Model summary of multiple regression analysis of uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) on brand attitude

Variable	Parameters	Coefficient	Std error	Tcal – value
Constant	β_0	3.795	0.063	59.876***
WOM (X_1)	β_1	0.144	0.012	11.975***
Publicity (X_2)	β_2	0.048	0.014	3.425***
R-Square (R^2)		0.406		
Adjusted R – Square (R^2)		0.402		
F – Statistics		103.358		
F – Probability		0.000		

***, **, and * denotes significance of coefficient at 1%, 5%, and 10% level respectively

Source: Field Survey, 2019 (SPSS Version 20)

The effect of uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) on brand attitude among customers was tested on table 4.7. The result shows that the estimated value of WOM (X_1), was statistically significant at 1% level of probability with a positive sign, implying that, an increase in WOM communication leads to increase in brand attitude by 0.144 unit. Hence, we can say that WOM communication has significant effect on brand attitude. The coefficient of publicity (X_2) was significant at 1% level of probability with a positive sign which implies that, publicity significantly affects customer brand attitude.

The R^2 coefficient of multiple determination was 0.406, which indicates that, 40.6% disparity in the dependent variable was explained by changes in the independent variables, while 59.4% was unexplained by the stochastic terms in the model. Thus, the independent variables (WOM and publicity) can only explain 40.6 percent of changes in brand attitude, leaving 59.4% unexplained. The R^2 adjusted was 40.2% indicating a goodness of fit of the regression model adopted in this study which is statistically significant at 5% probability level. More so, the f-statistical value of 103.358 was observed and f-probability value of 0.000 was also observed from the analysis which is less than 0.05 (95% of freedom), indicating that estimated regression model adopted in this study is statistically significant at 5% level. With this, the researchers rejected the null hypothesis and accepted alternate hypothesis. Hence, uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity), do significantly affect consumers brand attitude towards GSM brands.

Test of hypothesis 3

Uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) do not significantly determine brand re-use intention. In order to test the hypothesis, two variables were identified as follows:

(i) Uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) as independent variables.

(ii) Brand re-use intention as dependent variable.

Model specification: Uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) is estimated to influence brand re-use intention as shown below;

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2) \dots\dots\dots 1$$

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e_i \dots 2$$

Where;

Y = Brand re-use intention

X₁ = WOM

X₂ = Publicity

β₀ = Intercept

β₁ – β₂ = Parameters estimate

e_i = error term (0.05%)

Therefore, $Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2$

Using the model above, the dependent and independent variables were subjected to regression analysis in order to generate the predicted influence of the independent variables X₁(WOM) and X₂ (Publicity) on the dependent variable Y (brand re-use intention) as shown on Table 4.8

Table 4.8: Model summary of multiple regression analysis of uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) on brand re-use intention

Variable	Parameters	Coefficient	Std error	Tcal – value
Constant	β ₀	0.821	0.310	2.650 ^{***}
WOM (X ₁)	β ₁	0.063	0.080	0.177
Publicity (X ₂)	β ₂	0.142	0.007	19.203 ^{***}
R-Square (R²)		0.515		
Adjusted R – Square (R⁻²)		0.512		
F – Statistics		184.602		
F – Probability		0.000		

***, **, and * denotes significance of coefficient at 1%, 5%, and 10% level respectively

Source: SPSS Version 20 Computation

The effect of uncontrolled communications on brand re-use intention among customers of telecommunication industry was tested in table 4.8. From the result, the estimated value of WOM (X₁) was statistically insignificant on brand re-use intention at 5% level. Thus, WOM has no significant effect on brand re-use intention among customers of telecommunication firms in South-South, Nigeria.

The predictable value of publicity (X₂) was statistically significant and positively related to brand re-use intention at 1% level. This implies that, publicity has significant effect on brand re-use intention in

telecommunications industry. In specific terms, a unit increase on the use of publicity, leads to 0.142 units of brand re-use intention. Thus, brand information obtained from news release, press conference significantly triggers brand re-use intention among customers of telecommunication firms in South-South, Nigeria.

The coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) was 0.515, which implies that, 51.5% variation observed in the dependent variable was described by changes in the independent variables, while 48.5% was unexplained by the stochastic variables in the model. In detail, the independent variables (WOM and publicity) were being explained by 51.5 percent variations in the dependent variable (brand re-use intention) while 48.5 percent was explained by the stochastic variable. F-stat value of 184.602 and F-prob value of 0.000 was observed from the analysis which is less than 0.05 (95% degree of freedom), indicating that, the estimated regression model adopted in this study was statistically significant at 5% significant level. With this, the null hypothesis was rejected in favour of the alternate hypothesis which stated that uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) do significantly determine consumers brand re-use intention.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the test of hypothesis one showed that there is a significant and positive effect of uncontrolled communications on brand preference for GSM brands in the South-South Zone of Nigeria. Both surrogates of the independent variables were statistically significant used individually and jointly. The means that WOM communications affects consumer brand preference as well as publicity. Thus, telecommunications companies can use these tools singly or jointly to induce brand preference in their consumers. This result agrees with the work of Oti, Odigbo and Bassey (2016), where a similar result was obtained from their examination of customer public relations practices on the corporate performance of commercial banks in the country with the result of the analysis stating that customer relations practices of commercial banks in Nigeria have significant effect on their corporate performance.

The result from the test of hypothesis two showed that uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) had a positive and significant effect on the brand attitude of subscribers of telecommunications companies in the South-South Zone of Nigeria. The result of the analysis clearly shows that a percentage increase in the uncontrolled communications will lead to a more than 40 percent increase in the brand attitude of subscribers of GSM brands to their various brands. This result is in agreement with the apriori expectations because unsolicited credible information about a company convinces more and leads to positive attitudes being formed for such company's products/services. Thus, the feeling consumers have toward a service brand can trigger intentions to buy and remain with the company/product.

Though the singular test for WOM effect on consumer brand re-use intention in hypothesis three showed an insignificant effect, the result from uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) indicated a positive and significant effect on the subscribers' brand re-use intention. This implies that WOM on its own has no significant effect on subscribers; brand re-use intentions, but when used together with publicity, its effect is both positive and significant as a unit increase in the WOM communications will lead to a more than 50% increase in the brand re-use intentions of subscribers of GSM brands.

Summary of Findings and Conclusion

From the results obtained from the test of hypotheses, it can be stated that there is a significant and positive effect of uncontrolled communications on the responses of consumers in terms of their brand preference, brand attitude and brand re-use intentions. Thus in conclusion, the null hypotheses were all rejected in favour of the alternative hypotheses which state that;

- H₁** There is a significant effect of uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) on the consumer preference for GSM brands.
- H₂** Uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) do significantly affect consumer attitude towards GSM brands.
- H₃** Uncontrolled communications (WOM and publicity) do significantly determine brand re-use intention.

Recommendations

In view of the above conclusions, the following recommendations were made;

- There is need for the studied firms to continue to build their service quality and delivery systems around integrity, credibility and humanity in order to enhance their companies' reputation and customers' trust which will make customers talk positively and persuasively about the firms. Equally, customer satisfaction should be one of the vital goals of the telecommunications companies because the offer of satisfactory services will induce favourable and kind words from subscribers which may enhance or detract from preference options in the studied area.
- The studied firms should continually aim at triggering uncontrolled communications and building structures that create positive brand images in the minds of target audiences which overtime will become the attitude of the subscribers. When the brand attitude of subscribers is set, it will be difficult for such customers to speak badly of their brand or the company.
- Lastly, continued patronage of the subscribers is what sustains companies. Therefore, it behooves on Management of the GSM companies to satisfy their customers beyond expectations to ensure that re-use intentions for particular brands are sustained. This re-use intention will emanate from the WOM communications and publicity carried out by the companies. Ensuring that positive WOM and positive publicity are maintained will go a long way to sustain re-use intentions. So the Management of the studied companies should do all that are necessary to maintain their public image

Suggestions for further Research

Several researches could be carried out on the individual domains of uncontrolled communications and consumer responses in other sectors such as;

- Effect of WOM on Consumer Brand Preference
- Effect of WOM on Consumer Brand Attitude
- Effect of WOM on Consumer Brand Re-use Intentions
- Effect of Publicity on Consumer Brand Preference
- Effect of Publicity on Consumer Brand Attitude
- Effect of Publicity on Brand Re-use Intentions

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